

THE ROLE, SIGNIFICANCE, AND PREVENTION OF VITAMIN B9 DEFICIENCY IN UNA-SANA CANTON CONSUMERS

Huska Jukić¹, Samira Dedić^{2*}, Aida Džaferović², Azira Hrnjica¹

¹University of Bihać, Faculty of Health Studies, 4, Nositelja hrvatskog trolista 4, 77000
Bihać, Bosnia and Herzegovina

²University of Bihać, Faculty of Biotechnology, Kulina Bana 2, 77000 Bihać, Bosnia and
Herzegovina

Introduction

Folic acid is a vitamin that belongs to the B group of vitamins, and is often referred to as vitamin B9. This is a group of twelve different vitamins that are numbered according to the order of discovery in science: B1, B2, B3, etc. Although each of these vitamins has a different chemical structure, they are classified into one group due to their common content in many foods, but also their common role in metabolism, immune response and normal function of the nervous system (Bundalo et al., 2013). The population of women of reproductive age is most affected by vitamin B9 deficiency because they have a greater need for folates in the periconceptional, prenatal and natal period. If they do not meet these increased needs for vitamin B9, miscarriages, premature births and congenital malformations can occur as a consequence, among which the two most common ones stand out; neural tube defect and anencephaly. Pregnancy planning strategies, promotion of vitamin B9 supplementation, compulsory fortification of foods with folic acid in certain countries and similar initiatives have led to a reduction in the incidence of diseases caused by folate deficiency and congenital disorders (Crider et al., 2011). Folic acid and folates are not one and the same, so they are two different forms of vitamin B9. Folates represent the natural form of this vitamin that can be found in food and in the body, while folic acid is a synthetic form of the vitamin used for the production of supplements of this vitamin or food fortification. An interesting fact is that folic acid is much better absorbed in the human body than folate (Barasi, 2003). Socioeconomic conditions are an important factor that hinders the availability of folate-rich foods in the daily diet of the general population (Miyaki et al., 2013). However, despite this, the recommended daily intake of 0.4 mg per day is certainly difficult to achieve through nutrition, so the idea came up that everyone would benefit from folate-enriched food. In order to reduce the incidence of neural tube defects, the US Food and Drug Administration (FDA) mandated that as of January 1, 1998, all cereal products must be fortified with 0.14 mg of folic acid per serving. 100 g of grain (Food and Drug Administration 1996). It has been estimated that this measure could enrich the daily intake of folate in adults by an average of 0.1 mg (Shojania and Kauster, 2010). Mandatory fortification of cereal products, such as wheat flour and bread made from wheat flour, is carried out in 72 countries around the world. In countries with mandatory flour fortification, folate status improved significantly and the rate of neural tube defects dropped by almost 80%. However, many countries do not implement mandatory fortification of cereals and their products (Huđek, 2015). The countries of the European Union have not agreed on the issue of food fortification with folic acid, but fortification is carried out

in some countries such as Great Britain (Babić, Božović and Vraneković, 2014). In Bosnia and Herzegovina, no law has been passed that would require employers in the food industry, who are engaged in the production or processing of cereals and cereal products, to be fortified with folic acid. However, on the BiH market, you can find foods enriched with folic acid, and these are mainly imported products, and these are most often various types of cereals intended for breakfast (cereal flakes or muesli). As far as flour is concerned, domestic products of BiH producers, which are not enriched with folic acid, are predominantly represented on the market. A new technology of triple fortification of salt with iodine, iron and folic acid is also under development. According to the given study, the costs for adding these micronutrients to salt would be about \$27 per person per year, which makes this technology profitable in the fight against the consequences of the deficit of the mentioned micronutrients (Modupe et al., 2021). The subject of this research is the role of vitamin B9 in the human body, and the importance of its intake through nutrition in disease prevention. The particularly important role of this vitamin is in the prevention of congenital malformations, which again indicates the importance of its sufficient intake for all women of reproductive age. There is a scientifically proven correlation between insufficient intake of vitamin B9 (folic acid and folate) on the one hand and an increase in the incidence of neural tube defects on the other hand, which result in severe diseases of newborns. Taking into account this scientific evidence and the eating habits of modern society, the recommended daily intake (RDA) of 400 mcg (Institute of Medicine. Food and Nutrition Board, 1998) for each adult is almost impossible to achieve through diet alone, and therefore fortification of foods with folic acid with appropriate supplementation is considered necessary in every society. Unfortunately, many countries do not have a system of mandatory fortification of foods with folic acid, nor a developed public health system for promoting the importance of folic acid supplementation, especially in pregnant and lactating women as the most vulnerable population in this context.

Materials and methods

According to this problem, the following research questions were defined:

- Are the citizens of Una-Sana Canton familiar with the term "folic acid"?
- How often do doctors recommend folic acid supplements to patients?
- How often do citizens consume folic acid supplements or other dietary supplements that contain folic acid (eg B complex vitamins, multivitamins, etc.)?
- What is the attitude of citizens towards folic acid; do they think that its intake is beneficial or harmful for people's health, especially pregnant and lactating women?
- What do citizens know about food fortification with folic acid and the need for folic acid supplements?

➤What do citizens think about promoting folic acid supplementation; is it useful for citizens to educate themselves or only for pharmaceutical companies as a marketing tool?

➤Based on the presented problem and defined research questions, the following research goal was set: The goal of this research was to examine and analyze the knowledge and attitudes of the consumers of the Una - Sana Canton towards vitamin B9.

Research methods

The following scientific methods were used in the work: synthesis method, analysis method, deductive method, inductive methods (incomplete, predicative and causal induction), concretization method, generalization method, specialization method, classification method, description method, compilation method, empirical-non-experimental (survey) method, statistical method, sample method and survey method (Radeka, 2018). In addition to these main ones, other scientific methods were used in the work. It should also be mentioned the limitations when collecting data that related to statistical data on the number of children born with any malformations in general in any area of Bosnia and Herzegovina (BiH). Thus, data on the number of cases of neural tube defects are unavailable on important information systems (Institute of Public Health at any administrative level, Federal Statistical Office, BiH Statistics Agency, etc.), and no scientific research papers published in domestic or foreign journals were found containing such information.

Research techniques and instruments

In this research work, the following techniques were used: survey technique and scaling technique. The instrument that was used to apply the survey technique was an online survey questionnaire compiled and conducted using an online tool, i.e. software for survey administration - "Google Forms". The survey questionnaire was anonymous and contained all closed-ended questions (see attachment 1), and was open for filling in for a period of 26 days (October 18, 2022 – November 12, 2022). It consisted of three parts: the first part with demographic data (a total of 4 questions; age, gender, education and place of residence) in which a nominal and interval scale was used. The second part consisted of three questions related to the research problem, where a nominal scale was used. The third part of the questionnaire related to the scales for measuring attitudes (consisting of four statements, each of which 23 statements has its contradictory counterpart, which checks the comprehensibility and sincerity of the answers; therefore, a total of 8 statements for scaling). The instrument for measuring attitudes used in this part of the questionnaire was a Likert scale. The tools used in the research work are: an electronic computer with software packages for word processing - MS Word, a software package for tabular calculations and creating graphs -MS Excel, online software for creating and conducting surveys - Google Forms and a calculator.

The sample (respondents) in the research

A total of 136 respondents participated in the research. According to the aim of the research, all respondents are from the area of the Una-Sana Canton. The number of respondents by

municipality was determined in such a way as to achieve representativeness of the sample, i.e. it was correlated according to the actual share of the population. The estimate of the total number of inhabitants in USK for the year 2020 was 266,535 inhabitants (Federal Bureau of Statistics, 2016; Una-Sana Canton in numbers, 2021), (Federal Bureau of Statistics, 2016). The number of respondents by municipality, as well as the estimated number of inhabitants, is shown in Table 1.

Table 1. Structure of respondents and residents according to municipalities in USK

Municipality	Number of respondents	Percentage of respondents	Number of inhabitants (in 2020)	Percentage of population (%)
Cazin	30	22	65239	24 %
Bihać	32	23	55805	21 %
Velika Kladuša	15	11	39994	15 %
Sanski Most	27	20	39651	15 %
Bosanska Krupa	10	7	24587	9 %
Bužim	9	7	19240	7 %
Ključ	7	5	15674	6 %
Bosanski Petrovac	6	4	6345	2 %
In total	136	100	266535	100 %

Results and discussion

From the attached table, it can be seen that the percentage of respondents from individual municipalities meets the representativeness of the sample. As for the gender structure of USK residents, the ratio of female to male population is balanced, with a slightly higher number of women (49.5% men: 50.5% women) (Federal Bureau of Statistics, 2020). When it comes to gender structure of the respondents, a much larger number of women were present. The survey questionnaire is structured in such a way that it classifies all respondents based on age into three groups: young age (from 15 to 44 years old), middle age (45-59 years old) and old age (60 and older). Out of a total of 136 respondents, 104 belong to the youth group, 19 to the middle age group and 13 to the elderly group. In real conditions, the youthful population is also dominant in USK, the middle-aged population is less numerous and the elderly population is the least numerous, which is also comparatively shown in the percentage shares. In the same way, a comparison was made between the structure of the respondents according to qualifications and the real conditions regarding professional training in USC. When the benefit of folic acid for the health of people, especially pregnant and lactating women, has been established, the next focus of scientific research is the understanding of its importance by the general public. As the emphasis was placed on the special importance of folic acid for the prevention of neural tube defects (NTD), most of the conducted surveys of attitudes and knowledge about folic acid in the general public were conducted precisely on the target population of women, both in the world and in our country. The tests are mainly based on women's general knowledge about folic acid, and then on its proper application, frequency of use, and which factors influence these attitudes; the correlation with socio-economic and demographic factors was most often examined. This research is somewhat different compared to previously conducted studies of attitudes about folic acid in our region, and it differs in that

the sample was taken from the general population and includes men. Thus, according to the results of this research, it can be seen that men have encountered the term folic acid much less and have less knowledge about its benefits for health compared to women. Out of a total of 69% of respondents who answered that they had heard of the term "folic acid" or "folate", as many as 83% of them were women, while the remaining 17% referred to men. Of the total number of respondents, 61% of them stated that they consumed very often folic acid supplements or some other dietary supplements that contained folic acid (e.g. vitamins of the B complex, multivitamins, etc.), and only 33% of the respondents received a doctor's advice to consume folic acid supplements. From the above, it can be assumed that most respondents took folic acid supplements on their own initiative or on the recommendation of someone else who is not a professional. 50% of respondents stated that folic acid is beneficial for human health, and 48% of respondents believe that insufficient intake of folic acid can have negative health consequences. On the other hand, a less than half number of respondents (40%) expressed a neutral attitude towards the claim that folic acid is beneficial for human health, and 42% of them also expressed a neutral attitude towards the negative consequences caused by the deficiency of this vitamin. This may indicate ignorance or an insufficient level of knowledge of USC citizens on this issue. 41% of respondents stated that folic acid should be used by pregnant and lactating women for the sake of normal development of the fetus (fetus, child), 17% of respondents denied this claim, while 42% of respondents expressed a neutral attitude. According to this relationship of respondents, the majority of USC citizens are not aware of the benefits of folic acid for normal fetal development; of the fetus; of a child. 22% of respondents believe that folic acid is artificially added to some foods that USC citizens buy and consume every day, and the same percentage (22%) of respondents believe that folic acid is not added to foods. The remaining 56% of respondents expressed a neutral attitude. Based on this ratio of positive, negative and neutral attitudes, it can be concluded that USC citizens are completely uneducated about the possible content of folic acid in the foods they buy every day, which can roughly indicate how much USC consumers read the declaration on food products and foodstuffs when shopping. 38% of respondents believe that promoting folic acid supplements is useful for all citizens and that more such promotions should be done. The same percentage (38% of respondents) denies the claim that only pharmaceutical companies benefit from the promotion of folic acid supplements and that their goal is only to make people buy more of their products. However, by a whole 10% more, that is, 48% of them expressed a neutral attitude towards the first statement about promoting folic acid supplements, and 33% of respondents were neutral towards the second statement; that only pharmaceutical companies benefit from it. A neutral attitude could point to the lack of interest of USC citizens on this topic, but the percentage of 38% of respondents, on the other hand, represents a good potential for initiating the mentioned promotions.

Garcia et al. (2018) conducted a descriptive qualitative survey of attitudes about the benefits of folic acid consumption among Pakistani, Bangladeshi and British mothers on the one hand and health workers on the other. The research instrument was a survey questionnaire, and the study results established similarities in opinions about the benefits of folic acid consumption among all three groups of mothers, regardless of the fact that they do not come from the same country. The study found that very few mothers consumed folic acid before conception, insufficient understanding of the benefits of using folic acid, and only a few respondents knew

how to list foods rich in folic acid. On the other hand, health workers widely believed that most mothers used folic acid before conception, 35 of which clearly indicates the wrong perception of health workers about the behavior of women, potential pregnant women. As for similar researches, by reviewing the relevant literature it is possible to find quite a few of them related to this topic, but as stated at the very beginning, mostly women, mothers, and pregnant women were included in the researches. Cui et al. (2021), on the basis of the reduced prevalence of NTDs in China in the period 2000-2017, which was associated with periconceptional supplementation of folic acid, conducted a study assessing the knowledge and actual use of folic acid among Chinese pregnant women, examining the factors that influenced the use of folic acid supplements. 428 pregnant women were included in the research, and the research instrument was an interview. 82% of respondents knew that folic acid can prevent neural tube defects. When asked if they had ever taken folic acid, 95% of the respondents answered yes.

64% of respondents from rural areas did not take folic acid supplements before conception, and 46% of them did. The probability that housewives and those who had an unplanned pregnancy will not start taking folic acid before pregnancy was also determined. By comparing the results of this research with the results obtained in this paper, the percentage of women who have ever consumed folic acid in China was higher than in the Una-Sana Canton. This is an expected order given that China previously implemented a strategy of periconceptional folic acid supplementation. As for our climate, a review of the relevant literature provides interesting information in an article in the scientific journal *Medica Jadertina* entitled "Folic acid - what do pregnant women in Zadar County know and how much it is used", which was published in 2011 by Vitale et al. The goal of this research was to determine how familiar mothers in Zadar County are with folic acid, and how much they were taking. The research instrument was an anonymous questionnaire, and the research was conducted in 2007 and lasted seven months. 340 women participated in the study. 80% of respondents answered that they know what folic acid is, and almost 85% of them believe that it is useful. 49% of the respondents received advice to consume folic acid, and the advice was mostly given by a doctor, while 39% of the respondents took some form of folic acid on their own initiative. Logistic regression showed that the main factors for taking folic acid are planned pregnancy and 36 spontaneous termination of pregnancy or stillbirth. Likewise, women with higher education consumed more folic acid compared to respondents with lower education, who are in a multiple disadvantageous position; in addition to insufficient education, they have no initiatives on supplementation either from the health system or from the social network to which they belong. In the Una Sana Canton, according to the results of this research, the same percentage as in the Zadar County, i.e. 83% of women stated that they had heard of the term folic acid. In the UnaSana Canton, 39% of respondents received advice from doctors to consume folic acid supplements, and in Zadar County, 49% of respondents. So, in Zadar County, doctors recommend the consumption of folic acid to female patients somewhat more often. Similar research was conducted in the Bjelovar-Bilogora County as part of the final thesis (Valentić, 2021) at the Faculty of Medicine of the University of Zagreb. The research was conducted in 2021 and lasted a total of five months, and included 209 pregnant women and new mothers, who filled out the survey questionnaire. The results of this test show that 70% of respondents know what folic acid is, and 88% of them believe that it is

beneficial for health. Of the respondents who stated that they took a folic acid preparation before conception, most of them (62%) received advice from a doctor, while a minority (25%) took the preparation on their own initiative. In Bosnia and Herzegovina, a study was conducted on the assessment of folic acid supplementation among pregnant women in BiH, which is the first study of its kind in this country. The research was conducted in 2015 and lasted about a month. The instrument was an online questionnaire that was available on a specialized portal for pregnant women and new mothers, and the main variable was the use of folic acid supplements. The research included 67 respondents. It is relevant to present only the fact that 88% of respondents stated that they used folic acid supplements at any time during pregnancy, and only 18% of respondents used folic acid supplements before conception (Djedjibegovic et al., 2020).

Conclusion

In the second half of the twentieth century, numerous studies were conducted that confirmed the link between low blood folate levels in women in the periconceptional period with a higher risk of neural tube defects (NTD). According to the research results of this paper, the following conclusion was reached: Citizens of the Una-Sana Canton are not sufficiently aware of the importance of folic acid for human health and its role in disease prevention. Women knew more about folic acid compared to men. Doctors rarely recommend folic acid supplementation to patients in the USC area, which could be particularly unfavorable for women in labor. USC consumers are not familiar with the possibility of fortifying foods with folic acid and do not know that folic acid is artificially added to some of the foods they consume every day. For the USC area, it is not possible to find statistical data on the number of newborns with a neural tube defect or any malformations in general, so it is not possible to question the connection of these cases with a low level of folate in the mother's blood. Recommendations for carrying out further research in the area of USC: First of all, it is necessary to initiate the public health system in this area to keep records of cases of newborn children with any malformations, which would represent a good basis for numerous scientific researches or, if records are already being carried out, to make these data easily available for the scientific research community of this canton. Likewise, keeping records of the frequency of hyperhomocysteinemia among the USC population could be linked to the incidence of cardiovascular diseases, which are considered the leading causes of mortality in the Federation of Bosnia and Herzegovina. Furthermore, it would be good to conduct a similar study on the most vulnerable population, i.e. to include only pregnant women and women giving birth, and to examine the actual use of folic acid by this population, in what doses and whether they know the right time to take folic acid supplements in order to prevent defects neural tubes. Likewise, the low socio-economic status of consumers in this canton could be linked to the frequency of the use of folic acid supplements.

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